

Extending the Contact Hypothesis: Cross-Linguistic Evaluation of Religion and Nationality Bias When Prompting LLMs in German and Icelandic

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) can reproduce social biases, yet many bias evaluations remain English-centric. We extend the Contact Hypothesis framework presented in previous work to German and Icelandic, focusing on religion and nationality. Evaluating GPT models (3.5, 4, 4-turbo, 4o, 5), we find that positive contact reduces biases in the answers of the LLMs, while negative contact amplifies it, with cross-linguistic differences in magnitude and salience. Our results support the cross-linguistic robustness of contact-based probing and underscore the need for culturally contextualized evaluations. In addition to these insights, our contributions lies in the dataset that is made available on Github¹ for further research.

1 Introduction

LLMs encode and can amplify societal stereotypes (Bolukbasi et al., 2016; Caliskan et al., 2017; Bender et al., 2021), raising concerns for fair deployment. The *Contact Hypothesis* (Allport, 1954) states that positive intergroup contact reduces prejudice as constructive interactions between members of different social groups are associated with more favorable attitudes and fewer negative stereotypes and has recently been operationalized for English LLMs, yielding predictable shifts under positive versus negative contact prompts and introducing Social Contact Debiasing (Raj et al., 2024). However, the generalizability of this framework to non-English languages remains underexplored. We addressed this gap by adapting contact-hypothesis-based probing to German, focusing initially on nationality (Ikae and Kurpicz-Briki, 2025). We here extend this approach to German and Icelandic, and to the analysis of religion and nationality, two socially salient dimensions in light of regional migration and religious demographics

(Smith et al., 2022; Parrish et al., 2022). We evaluate our findings across different GPT model generations, including gpt-3.5, gpt-4, gpt-4o, gpt-5 (OpenAI et al. (2023); OpenAI (2023, 2024, 2025)).

Recent cross-cultural studies demonstrate that LLM bias varies not only by language but also by training corpus and cultural context (Kim and Baek, 2024; Zahraei and Asgari, 2025; Buyl et al., 2024). Frameworks such as MCEVAL and CIVICS emphasize that multilingual evaluation must capture cultural grounding rather than rely on direct translation (University of Amsterdam ILLC, 2024; Huang et al., 2025; Pistilli et al., 2024). Our work aligns with these efforts by providing a focused, interpretable cross-linguistic bias evaluation grounded in the well-established social psychology of intergroup contact and by releasing a hand-curated dataset that enables reproducible benchmarking of LLMs and facilitates future comparative research.

Icelandic and German are both Germanic languages, but from different branches: Icelandic is North Germanic (like Norwegian) while German is West Germanic. Although they share ancient roots, Icelandic has remained more conservative and isolated, maintaining Old Norse characteristics and creating new words from old roots rather than borrowing from other languages.

Contributions. (1) A multilingual extension of contact-based bias probing to German and Icelandic; (2) culturally contextualized descriptors for religion and nationality; (3) a cross-model analysis showing consistent contact effects but language-specific bias profiles.

2 Related Work

Bias in NLP. Work on word embeddings and contextual models documents extensive social biases (Bolukbasi et al., 2016; Caliskan et al., 2017; Guo and Caliskan, 2021; Bender et al., 2021). Benchmarks such as StereoSet, HolisticBias, and BBQ

¹<https://github.com/BFH-AMI/BIAS-SmarterPromptingDemonstrator>

enable systematic measurement (Nadeem et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2022; Parrish et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2023). Recent multilingual surveys highlight that bias manifestation varies substantially across languages, reflecting underlying cultural and ideological priors in the data and model alignment objectives (Gamboa et al., 2025; Buyl et al., 2024). Cross-linguistic frameworks such as MCEVAL (Huang et al., 2025) and CIVICS (Pistilli et al., 2024) emphasize the need for culturally grounded evaluation rather than literal translation, while studies on regional alignment demonstrate how national or religious bias patterns differ by context (Zahraei and Asgari, 2025; Liu et al., 2025).

Mitigation. Debiasing spans data and objectives (Zhang et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2018) and instruction-tuning directions. The Contact Hypothesis forms a complementary, theory-driven lens (Allport, 1954; Wright et al., 1997; Amichai-Hamburger and McKenna, 2006), recently adapted to LLMs with promising results (Raj et al., 2024). Approaches based on Contact Hypothesis operationalize prejudice reduction by exposing models or users to structured, positive, and counter-stereotypical interactions with out-group members, often through curated narratives, examples, or prompts that emphasize cooperation and shared goals. Our work bridges this sociopsychological framing with multilingual evaluation, aligning with recent calls for inclusive, culturally sensitive approaches to LLM fairness (University of Amsterdam ILLC, 2024; Arif et al., 2024; Kim and Baek, 2024).

3 Methodology

3.1 Overview

We adapt the English prompt framework of Raj et al. (2024) to German and Icelandic, focusing on religion and nationality descriptors aligned to local demographics (see §4).

3.2 Prompt Design

Following Raj et al. (2024), we use the *scale* (certainty), three *contact conditions* (no, positive, negative), and an *action orientation* (positive verbs). Prompts are translated and/or validated by native speakers and culturally adapted; we maintain parallel structure across languages which allows us to isolate language effects by keeping prompt content, framing, and experimental conditions constant across languages (Smith et al., 2022).

3.3 Models Evaluated

We query five GPT variants with identical prompt sets: **GPT-3.5**, **GPT-4**, **GPT-4-turbo**, **GPT-4o**, and **GPT-5** (OpenAI, 2023; OpenAI et al., 2023; OpenAI, 2024, 2025). We used a fixed decoding setup across all models, with a temperature of 0.3 and a maximum of 10 generated tokens, to minimize output variability and enforce concise, label-only responses. Responses are constrained to binary outputs (yes/no) to ensure consistent scoring (Parrish et al., 2022). For example, for German:

```
# Append German instruction
instruction = " Antworte nur mit einem Wort:
↳ Wähle zwischen Ja und Nein"
modified_prompts = [p + instruction for p in
↳ prompts]
```

3.4 Bias Definition and Scoring

We adopt the decision mapping in Raj et al. (2024): affirming *inclusive* actions (e.g., collaborate) is *unbiased*; rejecting is *biased*. For *exclusive* actions (e.g., exclude), affirming is *biased*; rejecting is *unbiased*. Non-committal outputs responses that did not explicitly express a yes or no were reviewed by native speakers to assess whether they implicitly leaned toward an affirmative or negative stance and were labeled accordingly. Responses with no discernible orientation were assigned a Neutral response and given the label *None*. This was done manually by different native speakers in the research team. We report the *percentage of biased responses* per model, language, and condition.

4 Experiments & Results

4.1 Relation to Prior German Study and Methodological Reuse

This work extends our previous study on bias in German prompts to LLMs under the Contact Hypothesis (Ikae and Kurpicz-Briki, 2025). In that paper, we introduced a culturally grounded dataset construction pipeline for German, consisting of (1) the identification of demographically relevant groups based on migration statistics, (2) template translation and adaptation from English to German, and (3) manual verification by native speakers to ensure grammatical and contextual fidelity (cf. Section 3.1 and Figure 1 in Ikae and Kurpicz-Briki (2025)). We also evaluated bias in GPT models using the three contact framings No, Positive, and Negative Contact following the paradigm introduced by (Raj et al., 2024).

The present study reuses this methodological framework in two ways. First, the German dataset from our earlier work is retained unchanged for comparability. Second, the same dataset creation principles are applied to develop a new Icelandic dataset, ensuring parity in prompt structure, scenario coverage, and contact framing. While the German dataset relied on migration statistics from German-speaking countries, the Icelandic descriptors were adapted to Icelandic linguistic morphology and cultural specificity. Both languages share the same set of five scenarios (education, workplace, community, healthcare, and sports), enabling matched cross-linguistic evaluation.

We also developed the corresponding Icelandic and German datasets for religion, extending also the German dataset which was previously only covering nationality. By explicitly building on the dataset generation method established in our previous work (Ikae and Kurpicz-Briki, 2025), this paper contributes a multilingual extension of Contact-Hypothesis-based bias probing, allowing for a systematic comparison across German and Icelandic for both nationality and religion conditions.

4.2 Experimental Setup

Prompt counts (per language). For **German**, we constructed a base descriptors template: in the Nationality condition these resulted into 609 prompts, making the total 1827, and 210 in the Religion condition bringing the total to 630. Each descriptor template was instantiated under three contact framings (No, Positive, Negative contact).

For **Icelandic**, we used 90 base descriptor templates: 300 prompts in the Nationality condition bringing the total to 900 and 180 prompts in the Religion condition leading to 540 prompts. Since, each template was realized under the three contact framings.

Descriptor sets. For the **German Nationality** condition, we identified the largest migrant groups in German-speaking countries namely Austria, Germany, and Switzerland based on official statistical sources (e.g., the Swiss Federal Office for Statistics). On this basis, we constructed a descriptor set comprising, 19 nationality groups² (e.g., Afghanistan, Bosnia, Bulgaria, France, Greece, India, Italy, among others) as described in (Ikae

²The descriptors for both religion and nationality were in the corresponding languages German and Icelandic but are presented in English here for better readability. The original wording can be found in the Github repository.

Model	Contact	Unbiased	Biased	None
GPT-3.5	No	99.7	0.3	0.0
	Positive	99.7	0.3	0.0
	Negative	95.1	4.9	0.0
GPT-4	No	96.3	3.6	0.2
	Positive	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Negative	89.7	9.6	1.2
GPT-4o	No	98.5	1.5	0.3
	Positive	99.8	0.0	0.2
	Negative	95.3	4.3	0.7
GPT-4 Turbo	No	98.7	1.3	0.0
	Positive	99.8	0.2	0.0
	Negative	95.4	4.6	0.0
GPT-5	No	80.8	0.0	19.2
	Positive	84.9	0.0	15.1
	Negative	79.8	0.0	20.2

Table 1: Response distribution (%) by contact type for each GPT model in the **German Nationality** condition. Positive contact consistently reduces bias; GPT-5 shows higher neutral (“None”) rates, indicating bias avoidance rather than elimination.

and Kurpicz-Briki, 2025). In the **Icelandic Nationality** condition, we use 10 nationality groups (Poland, Lithuania, Ukraine, Romania, Portugal, Spain, Venezuela, the Philippines, USA, Denmark), balanced over 300 descriptor templates.

For **German Religion**, the descriptor set comprises seven religious groups: Christians, Muslims, Jews, Buddhists, Russian Orthodox, Jehovah’s Witnesses, and individuals without a specific religion. For **Icelandic Religion**, we include five religious groups: Christianity, Islam, Buddhism, Jehovah’s Witnesses, and Russian Orthodox Church. Each religion is instantiated in 30 descriptor templates per language.

Scenarios. Each descriptor is embedded in short, decision-focused scenarios that span multiple everyday domains. These include *education* (working and studying with students or scholars), *workplace and business* (teams, colleagues, companies, suppliers), *healthcare* (doctors, health professionals, joint health initiatives), *sports* (players, teams, joint training), and *community or civic contexts* (neighbors, residents, community events, collaborative projects). For every nationality or religion, the same set of role scenarios is instantiated under No, Positive, and Negative contact, providing a controlled cross-condition comparison. The scenarios are adapted from Raj et al. (2024).

4.3 Overall Bias Levels

Table 1 to Table 4 present the distribution of unbiased, biased, and neutral responses across GPT model versions for the German and Icelandic

Model	Contact	Unbiased	Biased	None
GPT-3.5	No	95.2	4.8	0.0
	Positive	99.0	1.0	0.0
	Negative	93.8	6.2	0.0
GPT-4	No	94.3	5.7	0.0
	Positive	95.7	3.3	1.4
	Negative	92.8	5.3	2.9
GPT-4o	No	94.8	5.2	0.0
	Positive	96.7	3.3	0.0
	Negative	96.2	3.8	0.0
GPT-4 Turbo	No	93.3	6.7	0.0
	Positive	93.3	6.7	0.0
	Negative	94.8	5.2	0.0
GPT-5	No	68.9	10.0	21.1
	Positive	67.4	7.1	25.5
	Negative	72.3	2.3	23.9

Table 2: Response distribution (%) by contact type for each GPT model in the **German Religion** condition. Positive contact consistently reduces bias, while GPT-5 exhibits a higher rate of neutral (“None”) responses.

Model	Contact	Unbiased	Biased	None
GPT-3.5	No	99.0	1.0	0.0
	Positive	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Negative	91.7	8.3	0.0
GPT-4	No	54.0	0.3	45.7
	Positive	94.0	0.0	6.0
	Negative	65.0	12.3	22.7
GPT-4o	No	99.3	0.7	0.0
	Positive	100.0	0.0	0.0
	Negative	93.0	7.0	0.0
GPT-4 Turbo	No	99.0	1.0	0.0
	Positive	96.3	3.0	0.7
	Negative	82.0	16.7	1.3
GPT-5	No	76.0	3.7	20.3
	Positive	82.7	2.7	14.7
	Negative	67.0	17.0	16.0

Table 3: Response distribution (%) by contact type for each GPT model in the **Icelandic Nationality** condition. Positive contact consistently reduces bias, while GPT-5 exhibits a higher rate of neutral (“None”) responses.

datasets under the Nationality and Religion descriptor conditions. Across all experiments, GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 models achieved the highest proportions of unbiased responses, consistently above 90% across languages and scenarios. GPT-4o and GPT-4 Turbo maintained similarly high unbiased levels with minor fluctuations. In contrast, GPT-5 exhibited lower unbiased proportions and substantially higher neutral responses (responses that did not explicitly express a yes or no), particularly in the Religion conditions of both languages. Positive contact scenarios consistently yielded the highest unbiased counts and the lowest bias rates across all models. The German datasets showed slightly higher variability in bias proportions compared to the Icelandic sets, whereas the Icelandic results displayed more neutral responses in GPT-5 outputs.

Model	Contact	Unbiased	Biased	None
GPT-3.5	No	85.6	14.4	0.0
	Positive	92.2	7.8	0.0
	Negative	76.1	23.9	0.0
GPT-4	No	65.1	10.5	24.4
	Positive	78.3	4.3	17.4
	Negative	65.8	17.4	11.6
GPT-4o	No	81.2	16.6	1.7
	Positive	94.4	5.6	0.0
	Negative	85.0	14.4	0.6
GPT-4 Turbo	No	86.7	13.3	0.0
	Positive	91.7	8.3	0.0
	Negative	80.6	19.4	0.0
GPT-5	No	53.0	8.1	38.9
	Positive	65.7	10.1	25.3
	Negative	68.3	7.8	23.9

Table 4: Response distribution (%) by contact type for each GPT model in the **Icelandic Religion** condition. Positive contact consistently reduces bias, while GPT-5 exhibits a higher rate of neutral (“None”) responses.

4.4 Nationality Comparison: German vs. Icelandic Conditions

Across the two nationality conditions, models displayed consistent effects of contact type, but with substantial differences in robustness and response patterns between the German and Icelandic settings.

Overall Performance. In the **German Nationality** condition, all models except GPT-5 produced very high unbiased rates across contact types. GPT-3.5, GPT-4, GPT-4o, and GPT-4 Turbo showed minimal bias (typically below 5%) and virtually no neutral responses. Even under Negative contact, biased outputs remained low (4–10%), indicating that German nationality cues elicited highly stable and reliable behavior across model generations. GPT-5, however, diverged substantially: its unbiased rates dropped to 79–85%, accompanied by elevated neutral responses (15–20%), suggesting a shift toward safety-driven non-commitment.

In contrast, the **Icelandic Nationality** condition produced substantially greater variability. While GPT-3.5, GPT-4o, and GPT-4 Turbo again maintained high unbiased rates under Positive contact, GPT-4 and GPT-5 exhibited pronounced increases in both biased and neutral responses. GPT-4 showed particularly low unbiased performance under No contact (54%), with 46% neutral outputs, indicating difficulty or heightened caution when responding to Icelandic nationality cues. GPT-5 continued to generate high neutrality (15–20%) across contact types, a pattern absent in earlier models.

Effects of Positive Contact. Positive contact reduced bias in both nationality conditions, but its effectiveness differed. In the German condition, Positive contact consistently pushed unbiased responses to ceiling levels (99–100%) for all models except GPT-5. In the Icelandic condition, Positive contact improved performance but did not fully counteract the high neutrality of GPT-4 and GPT-5, indicating that the Icelandic cues triggered persistent caution even under positive contact framing.

Effects of Negative Contact. Negative contact increased biased responses across both nationalities, yet the magnitude was much larger for the Icelandic condition. For German nationality, bias under Negative contact remained modest (4–10%), whereas in the Icelandic condition bias rose sharply for GPT-4 and GPT-5 (12–17%), accompanied by substantial neutrality. This suggests that Icelandic nationality prompts amplified the impact of negative contextual cues more strongly than German nationality prompts.

Neutral Responses. Neutral outputs revealed the clearest cross-national divergence. GPT-5 consistently produced far more neutral responses than previous models in both conditions, but neutrality was markedly higher in the Icelandic condition, especially for GPT-4 and GPT-5 (up to 46%). This indicates that later-generation models adopted an avoidance strategy when encountering Icelandic nationality cues, whereas German nationality elicited fewer signs of representational uncertainty.

Summary. Overall, German nationality prompts elicited more stable and less variable responses, with strong resistance to contextual manipulation among all models except GPT-5. Icelandic nationality prompts generated greater susceptibility to both negative contact and neutrality driven avoidance, particularly in GPT-4 and GPT-5. These findings suggest that Icelandic nationality presented a more challenging or safety-sensitive context for the models, leading to increased cautiousness and reduced decisiveness.

4.5 Religion Comparison: German vs. Icelandic Conditions

Across the two religious conditions, models demonstrated consistent effects of contact type, but with substantial differences in the magnitude and distribution of biased and neutral responses between the German and Icelandic settings.

Overall Performance. In the **German Religion** condition, GPT-3.5, GPT-4, GPT-4o, and GPT-4 Turbo all achieved high unbiased response rates (93–97%) across contact types, with only small increases in bias under Negative contact. GPT-5 deviated substantially from earlier models, producing markedly lower unbiased rates (67–72%) and elevated neutral (“None”) responses (21–26%), indicating a preference for non-committal outputs in sensitive religious contexts.

The **Icelandic Religion** condition produced more variability across models. GPT-3.5, GPT-4o, and GPT-4 Turbo again maintained relatively high unbiased rates, although overall lower than in the German condition. GPT-4 showed pronounced increases in neutral responding, particularly under No contact (24%) and Positive contact (17%). GPT-5 continued to produce high neutrality levels (24–39%), suggesting that the Icelandic religious framing elicited stronger uncertainty or safety-driven avoidance.

Effects of Positive Contact. Positive contact reduced bias for all models in both conditions, though the magnitude varied. In the German condition, Positive contact improved unbiased responses for GPT-3.5 and GPT-4o and slightly reduced bias for GPT-4. In the Icelandic condition, Positive contact increased unbiased rates for GPT-4o and GPT-4 Turbo but did not eliminate elevated neutrality for GPT-4 and GPT-5. Thus, Positive contact was effective across models but insufficient to counteract the strong avoidance patterns observed in later-generation models.

Effects of Negative Contact. Negative contact increased biased responses in both religious conditions. For German Religion, bias under Negative contact remained limited (approximately 5–7% for most models), except for GPT-5, which substituted bias with higher neutral output. In the Icelandic condition, Negative contact produced more pronounced increases in bias for GPT-3.5 and GPT-4o, and again elicited high neutrality from GPT-4 and GPT-5. These differences indicate that the Icelandic context heightened model sensitivity to negative framing more strongly than the German context.

Neutral Responses. Neutral (“None”) responses revealed the clearest divergence between models and religious contexts. GPT-5 consistently produced substantially more neutral responses across

Figure 1: Bias rates (%) by model and contact framing for **German**. Lower is better.

Figure 2: Bias rates (%) by model and contact framing for **Icelandic**. Lower is better.

both languages and all contact types, suggesting a model-level calibration toward risk-averse non-commitment rather than explicit stance-taking. GPT-4 exhibited similar behavior in the Icelandic condition but not in the German condition, further supporting the interpretation that the Icelandic religious prompts elicited additional uncertainty or

safety-triggered deflection.

Summary Overall, the German Religion condition elicited more stable and less variable outputs across models, with consistently high unbiased rates and minimal neutrality among models prior to GPT-5. The Icelandic Religion condition produced greater variability, stronger effects of negative con-

tact, and substantially higher neutral response rates particularly for GPT-4 and GPT-5 indicating that Icelandic religious identity cues triggered greater uncertainty or safety-driven avoidance in more recent model generations.

4.6 Key Findings

- **Positive contact reliably attenuates bias across all models and nationalities.** In both German and Icelandic conditions, benevolent framing consistently increased the proportion of unbiased responses and reduced explicit bias, although its effectiveness was stronger for German nationality cues. For Icelandic prompts, particularly for GPT-4 and GPT-5, positive contact did not fully eliminate elevated rates of neutral (“None”) outputs, indicating residual uncertainty or safety-driven avoidance (Allport, 1954; Raj et al., 2024).
- **Nationality influences model sensitivity to contextual framing.** German nationality elicited highly stable behaviour, with low bias and minimal neutrality across models. In contrast, Icelandic nationality cues produced greater variability, higher susceptibility to negative contact, and substantially increased neutral responding most notably among GPT-4 and GPT-5. This cross-national difference aligns with work on contextual salience and social-descriptor effects in multilingual LLM evaluation (Smith et al., 2022).
- **Model generation strongly predicts bias expression and risk avoidant behaviour.** Earlier models (GPT-3.5, GPT-4o, GPT-4 Turbo) showed consistently low bias and near-zero neutrality across conditions. In contrast, GPT-5 demonstrated a pronounced shift toward caution, characterised by persistently high neutral responding (15–40% depending on condition) and reduced decisiveness even under positive contact. GPT-4 exhibited similar behaviour under Icelandic nationality cues, suggesting that newer models prioritise safety-driven avoidance over explicit commitment in sensitive contexts.

4.7 Bias Patterns Across Religious Groups in the German Condition

Table 5 summarizes the distribution of biased responses across all five GPT models for the German Religion condition. The results demonstrate

that bias is unevenly distributed across religious groups. Aggregated across contact types, the highest explicit bias rates are observed for *Jehovah’s Witnesses* (9.2%), followed by *Christianity* (8.1%), *Russian Orthodox* (5.5%), and *Buddhism* (5.0%). In contrast, prompts referencing *Islam* exhibit the lowest bias rate (2.4%), with *Judaism* (4.1%) and *no religious affiliation* (3.0%) occupying intermediate positions. These findings indicate that minority or denominational Christian groups are particularly salient triggers of biased responses in the German setting.

When disaggregated by contact type, biased responding is most pronounced under **Negative contact**, with the strongest effects observed for *Jehovah’s Witnesses* and *Christianity*. Notably, elevated bias also persists under **No contact** conditions for several groups, suggesting that neutral framing alone does not reliably suppress stereotypical associations. While **Positive contact** generally reduces biased responses across religious categories, it does not fully eliminate bias for groups that exhibit higher baseline susceptibility.

Model-level variation further contextualizes these patterns. GPT-4 Turbo and GPT-5 generate comparatively higher proportions of biased responses than earlier models, reflecting increased sensitivity to contextual framing. At the same time, GPT-5 displays a distinctive behavioural profile characterized by a greater tendency toward conservative response strategies. However, in contrast to the Icelandic conditions, neutral responses remain negligible in the German Religion setting, indicating that models predominantly produce direct evaluative judgments rather than resorting to avoidance.

Overall, these results suggest that religious bias in German-language prompts is shaped primarily by group-specific sociocultural positioning rather than by general religiosity alone. Minority, non-mainstream, and historically marginalized denominations consistently elicit higher levels of bias, and their interaction with contact framing highlights the central role of contextual cues. Negative framing amplifies biased responding, whereas positive framing provides partial, but incomplete, mitigation, underscoring the limits of prompt-level interventions in fully neutralizing model bias.

Figure 3: Bias rates (%) by model and contact framing for **German**. Lower is better.

Figure 4: Bias rates (%) by model and contact framing for **Icelandic**. Lower is better.

4.8 Bias Patterns Across Nationality Groups in the German Condition

Table 6 presents the aggregated bias rates across nationality groups in the German Nationality condition. Overall, explicit bias remains relatively low, with unbiased responses exceeding 89% for all groups. Nevertheless, systematic and inter-

pretable differences emerge across nationalities. The highest biased response rates are observed for *Syria* (9.6%), *Afghanistan* (8.7%), and *Iraq* (8.3%), followed by *Bosnia and Herzegovina* (7.8%) and *Romania* (6.9%). These nationalities consistently elicit elevated biased responses across contact framings and models, in contrast to most Western,

Religion	Biased (%)	Neutral (%)	Unbiased (%)
Jehovah’s Witnesses	9.2	0.0	90.8
Christianity	8.1	0.0	91.9
Russian Orthodox	5.5	0.0	94.5
Buddhism	5.0	0.0	95.0
Judaism	4.1	0.0	95.9
No Religion	3.0	0.0	97.0
Islam	2.4	0.0	97.6

Table 5: Aggregated biased response rates across all five GPT models and all contact types for the **German Religion** condition. Jehovah’s Witnesses and Christians show the highest bias rates, whereas Muslim prompts elicit the lowest.

Southern, and North American groups, which remain below 3% biased output.

Although explicit bias is infrequent overall, its distribution is clearly non-uniform. Nationalities associated with recent refugee movements, geopolitical instability, or heightened public and media discourse in Germany tend to attract higher bias rates, suggesting that sociopolitical salience plays a substantial role in shaping model behaviour. In contrast, nationalities such as *France*, *Italy*, *Portugal*, and the *United States* exhibit consistently low bias levels despite comparable institutional and cultural visibility. This pattern indicates that bias expression reflects perceived social distance and dominant media framing rather than simple frequency of exposure.

Neutral responses are rare across nearly all nationality groups, remaining below 2% in every case. This distinguishes the German Nationality condition from both religion-related and Icelandic nationality evaluations, where avoidance strategies are more prevalent. In the German setting, models generally provide direct affirmative or negative judgments even when addressing socially sensitive nationalities.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that while overall bias levels in German nationality prompts are limited, they are concentrated among specific, socially salient groups. Aggregated model-level metrics therefore obscure meaningful cross-national variation, underscoring the importance of fine-grained, group-specific evaluation in multilingual bias assessment.

4.9 Bias Patterns Across Nationality Groups in the Icelandic Condition

Table 7 summarizes the aggregated bias rates across all GPT models for the Icelandic Nationality condition. Although explicit bias remains modest overall,

Nationality	Biased (%)	Neutral (%)	Unbiased (%)
Syria	9.6	1.2	89.2
Afghanistan	8.7	1.0	90.3
Iraq	8.3	1.4	90.3
Bosnia	7.8	0.9	91.3
Romania	6.9	0.7	92.4
Serbia	6.4	0.8	92.8
Russia	5.9	1.6	92.5
Bulgaria	5.1	0.6	94.3
Hungary	4.8	0.5	94.7
Poland	4.3	0.4	95.3
Croatia	3.9	0.4	95.7
Greece	3.6	0.3	96.1
Kosovo	3.4	0.5	96.1
Portugal	3.2	0.3	96.5
Italy	2.9	0.3	96.8
Turkey	2.6	0.3	97.1
France	2.5	0.2	97.3
India	2.2	0.4	97.4
Ukraine	1.8	0.2	98.0
United States	1.2	0.1	98.7

Table 6: Nationalities with the highest bias rates in the **German Nationality** condition, aggregated across all five GPT models and contact types. Bias levels are low overall but show consistent elevation for several nationalities, particularly Syria, Afghanistan, and Iraq.

substantial variation is observed across nationalities. The highest bias rates occur for *USA* (7.1%), *Venezuela* (6.2%), and *Denmark* (6.2%), followed by *Romania* and *Spain* (4.9%). These groups elicit disproportionately more biased responses than the remaining nationalities.

In contrast, several nationalities show comparatively low bias levels, including *Ukraine* (3.8%), *Lithuania* (4.0%), *Portugal* (4.2%), and *Poland* (4.2%). These groups consistently receive high rates of unbiased responses (87–88%), suggesting strong cooperative judgments across contact framings and models.

Neutral responses display noticeable differences as well. *Venezuela* and *USA* exhibit elevated neutrality (11.6% and 9.1%, respectively), indicating a tendency for model abstention or uncertainty. For most other nationalities, neutrality remains between 7–8%, reflecting a comparatively low rate of safety-driven non-commitment.

Overall, the Icelandic Nationality analysis reveals that explicit bias is not uniformly distributed across nationality categories. Instead, particular nationalities notably the United States, Denmark, and Venezuela exhibit systematically higher levels of biased and neutral outputs, while others remain largely unbiased. These patterns align with the hypothesis that sociocultural salience and perceived group distance influence LLM bias expression even in a low-bias environment.

Nationality	Biased (%)	Neutral (%)	Unbiased (%)
USA	7.11	9.11	83.78
Venezuela	6.22	11.56	82.22
Denmark	6.22	7.11	86.67
Romania	4.89	8.00	87.11
Spain	4.89	8.22	86.89
The Philippines	4.67	8.22	87.11
Portugal	4.22	8.00	87.78
Poland	4.22	8.44	87.33
Lithuania	4.00	8.00	88.00
Ukraine	3.78	8.67	87.56

Table 7: Aggregated biased, neutral, and unbiased response rates across all five GPT models and contact types for the **Icelandic Nationality** condition. Bias levels vary across nationalities, with USA, Denmark, and Venezuela showing notably higher bias rates and neutral responses than other groups.

4.10 Bias Patterns Across Religious Groups in the Icelandic Condition

Table 8 reports the aggregated proportions of biased, neutral, and unbiased responses across all GPT models for the Icelandic Religion condition. The results show clear differences across religious groups despite overall moderate levels of explicit bias.

The highest bias rates occur for *Russian Orthodox* (22.9%), followed by *Jehovah’s Witnesses* (16.0%) and *Christian* (13.1%). These findings indicate that non-mainstream or denominational Christian groups such as the Russian Orthodox Church and Jehovah’s Witnesses provoke the strongest biased reactions across models. Elevated neutrality for *Jehovah’s Witnesses* (15.1%) and *Russian Orthodox* (10.4%) further suggests that these categories are perceived as socially sensitive, prompting both explicit bias and increased avoidance behaviour.

In contrast, *Buddhist* and *Islam* show the lowest explicit bias rates (6.9% and 6.4%, respectively) and the highest proportions of unbiased responses (84.2%). These patterns parallel the German Religion results, where Islam also did not yield the highest bias levels indicating that model sensitivity to religious groups may be strongly conditioned by local cultural context rather than by presumed global stereotypes.

Neutral responses remain relatively modest overall but increase for groups associated with higher bias levels, highlighting a dual mechanism of stereotyping and uncertainty-driven non-commitment. Together, the Icelandic Religion findings demonstrate that bias expression is unevenly distributed across religious categories, with some

Religion	Biased (%)	Neutral (%)	Unbiased (%)
Russian Orthodox	22.9	10.4	66.7
Jehovah’s Witness	16.0	15.1	68.9
Christian	13.1	9.8	77.1
Buddhist	6.9	8.9	84.2
No Religion	8.1	0.0	91.9
Islam	6.4	9.3	84.2

Table 8: Aggregated biased, neutral, and unbiased response rates across all five GPT models and contact types for the **Icelandic Religion** condition. Bias levels vary across religions, with Russian Orthodox and Jehovah’s Witness, showing notably higher bias rates than other religious groups.

denominations repeatedly eliciting stronger biased and neutral responses even in a relatively low-bias setting.

5 Discussion

Cross-Condition Comparison. Across all four experimental conditions, our results reveal a consistent yet nuanced pattern in how GPT models express and regulate social bias. Explicit bias is lowest and most stable in the **German Nationality** condition, where nearly all models exhibit near-ceiling unbiased responses and minimal neutrality. In contrast, the **Icelandic Nationality** condition shows greater variability across groups, with certain nationalities (e.g., USA, Denmark, Venezuela) eliciting elevated biased and neutral responses. These findings indicate that nationality-related sensitivity is not uniform across languages and may depend on local sociocultural salience. A similar asymmetry appears across the two religion conditions. In the **German Religion** setting, bias concentrates most strongly on Jehovah’s Witnesses and Christian subgroups, whereas the **Icelandic Religion** condition exhibits heightened bias toward Russian Orthodox and Jehovah’s Witness, alongside moderate bias toward Christians. Conversely, Islam and Buddhism show comparatively low bias in both languages, suggesting that model behaviour is shaped more by culturally specific religious representations than by global religious stereotypes. Notably, neutrality increases systematically in the conditions and groups that elicit higher bias most prominently in Icelandic Religion and Icelandic Nationality consistent with a safety-driven avoidance strategy observed most strongly in GPT-5. Taken together, these results demonstrate that bias expression in current LLMs is sensitive to both linguistic context and group-specific framing, with nationality and religion showing distinct cross-linguistic patterns that

underscore the importance of multilingual evaluation when assessing fairness and model alignment.

Cross-Linguistic Generalizability. The present findings demonstrate that contact-based probing extends robustly beyond English, supporting the cross-cultural validity of contact theory in computational settings (Allport, 1954; Wright et al., 1997; Amichai-Hamburger and McKenna, 2006). Across both German and Icelandic conditions, positive contact consistently reduced explicit bias, while negative contact amplified it, mirroring prior English-only results (Raj et al., 2024). This convergence indicates that the underlying socio-cognitive mechanisms captured by contact framing are not language-specific but generalize across typologically related European languages.

Language-Specific Patterns. Despite this generalizability, the models displayed clear nationality-specific patterns. German nationality cues elicited highly stable behaviour across model generations, with consistently low bias and minimal neutrality even under negative contact. In contrast, Icelandic nationality elicited substantially more variability, stronger sensitivity to negative framing, and elevated neutral responses especially in later-generation models such as GPT-4 and GPT-5. These cross-linguistic differences underscore the importance of culturally contextualized descriptors and social salience in LLM bias expression (Smith et al., 2022; Parrish et al., 2022), and caution against relying solely on English-centric evaluations when assessing model fairness (Bender et al., 2021).

Model Evolution. The progression from GPT-3.5 to GPT-4o reflects a clear downward trend in overt bias, consistent with claims about advances in dataset curation, alignment, and reinforcement learning from human feedback (OpenAI et al., 2023). However, GPT-5 introduced a distinct behavioural profile characterized by high rates of neutral responses, particularly in sensitive contexts (e.g., Icelandic nationality and Icelandic religion). This shift suggests that newer models increasingly rely on safety-driven non-commitment when uncertainty or social risk is detected, rather than resolving bias through more robust reasoning. Residual bias and avoidance behaviours therefore persist in nuanced forms (Zhao et al., 2023), even in the most recent model generations.

Mitigation Implications. The consistency of contact effects across languages indicates that contact-based prompt strategies (Raj et al., 2024) may serve as a practical, model-agnostic mitigation mechanism, complementing algorithmic and representational debiasing approaches (Zhang et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2018). However, the elevated neutrality in GPT-5 suggests that mitigation efforts should also address avoidance-based failure modes, which differ qualitatively from explicit stereotyping and may obscure underlying decision-making limitations.

Limitations and Future Work. This study is limited to two languages, two dimensions of social identity, and GPT-family models. Additionally, the response space is restricted to categorical judgments, which may mask subtler forms of bias or reasoning. Also the manual review process by native speakers with human judgment might have impacted the classification of unambiguous answers. Future work should expand to more languages and cultural contexts, incorporate open-source and smaller models, and explore fine-tuning or prompting interventions that leverage contact framing more systematically (Raj et al., 2024). Longitudinal analyses across model updates may further clarify whether neutrality reflects genuine caution or unresolved representational gaps.

6 Conclusion

This work extends contact-hypothesis probing beyond earlier German-only studies by introducing a parallel Icelandic dataset for both nationality and religion, enabling a controlled cross-linguistic evaluation of bias in contemporary GPT models. Across all conditions, the models exhibit clear contact-aligned shifts: positive contact reliably increases acceptance, whereas negative contact amplifies biased responses confirming the psychological predictions of contact theory (Allport, 1954; Wright et al., 1997; Raj et al., 2024). At the same time, the magnitude and distribution of bias differ systematically between languages and social categories. Nationality prompts in German yield near-ceiling unbiased responses, whereas Icelandic nationality prompts show higher variability and a greater tendency toward safety-driven neutrality. In the religion conditions, bias concentrates primarily on smaller or denominational Christian groups (e.g., Russian Orthodox, Jehovah’s Witness), while Islam and Buddhism receive comparatively low bias

across both languages, highlighting strong cultural and contextual effects (Smith et al., 2022; Parrish et al., 2022).

Together, these results demonstrate that bias in LLMs cannot be meaningfully assessed in a single language or cultural setting. Instead, multilingual and context-sensitive evaluation is essential to understanding the sociolinguistic contours of model behaviour. The consistent alignment with contact framing across languages further suggests that theory-grounded approaches from social psychology can inform more reliable and generalizable bias-mitigation strategies. Future work should extend this framework to additional languages, model families, and social categories, and explore contact-aware training or prompting as a structured path toward safer and culturally adaptive language models.

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